

IMPROVING THE READING LEVEL OF GRADE VI GRAPPLING READERS THROUGH PROJECT SEL-P (Strategic Enhancement Learning-Package)

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this study is to help build the reading level of the Grade 6 Grappling readers of Maximino S. Lazaro Integrated School through Project SEL-P (Strategic Enhancement Learning-Package), a contextualized reading material crafted by the proponents themselves. The research addressed the following questions: the reading level of the Grade 6 learners before and after the implementation of the intervention, the effectiveness of Project SEL-P in improving the reading level of Grade 6 Grappling readers and the insights gained of the parents and Grade 6 learners on Project SEL-P. Using pre-experimental one group pretest-posttest design, 9 out of 35 learners assessed during the pretest (who scored 0-10 of reading words or Level 1) were selected. Data was collected using the Quick RAP tool developed by the Curriculum Implementation Division (CID) of Masbate Province. Using paired sample T-Test, with 95% confidence level, result shows that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and posttest scores. Posttest results show that 9 out of 9 learners under the Grappling Level showed significant improvement in their reading level. Seven (7) learners are on Advancing which means that their reading level is on Level 4 while two (2) learners belong to Establishing and/or the reading level is on Level 3. The pupils reading level improve from Level 1 to Level 3 and Level 4 with a descriptive level of Establishing and Advancing. It indicates that learners reading level had improved after the reading intervention. Based on this finding, it is recommended that this study be widely implemented among schools with struggling readers. Embracing this method can lessen non-readers in school. Teachers are advised to benchmark, adopt and adapt this method in reinforcing learner's reading level as it has demonstrated effectiveness in facilitating meaningful reading experience.

Keywords: *Reading Level, Grappling Readers and Strategic Learning Enhancement Package*

INTRODUCTION

Reading plays a vital role in the learning process. It is one of the macro skills of communication that can be correlated to the academic performance of the students. Before the pandemic, it is a common struggle for teachers on how to uplift the reading performance of the pupils. It is indeed taxing for public school teachers to deliver quality education in a new normal setting. These readers require remedial training in skills that they were lacking in earlier grades. For many years, the pupils have been given assignments that are far too tough for them to satisfactorily complete alone. It is no surprise then, that they are scared. Thus, they avoid reading for the most part and have developed maladaptive coping techniques when presented with scholastic responsibilities.

Literature and studies pertaining to the challenges faced by grappling readers in Grade VI illuminate the multifaceted nature of reading difficulties within this demographic. Research indicates that factors such as insufficient vocabulary knowledge, limited fluency, inadequate comprehension strategies, and socio-emotional barriers contribute to the reading struggles experienced by these students (Guthrie et al., 2012; National Center for Education Statistics, 2020). Moreover, the transition to middle school often exacerbates these challenges, as students confront increasingly complex texts and academic expectations (Kamil et al., 2008).

Concurrently, literature exploring the intersection of literacy instruction and Social and Emotional Learning provides compelling evidence for the efficacy of integrated approaches in addressing the needs of struggling readers (Durlak et al., 2011; Elias et al., 1997). SEL frameworks, characterized by their emphasis on self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship skills, and responsible decision-making, offer a holistic lens through which to scaffold literacy development (CASEL, 2020).

By nurturing students' socio-emotional competencies alongside targeted reading instruction, interventions like SEL-P possess the potential to engender enduring improvements in both academic performance and socio-emotional well-being. Lastly, Bonganciso (2016) found out that Contextualized Teaching and Learning's effects on the reading comprehension performance of thirty-three Bachelor of Science in Information Technology students were investigated. The pupils' reading comprehension performance improved significantly from the pretest to the posttest. As a result, when reading activities are contextualized, positive benefits on learners' reading comprehension ability can be seen.

To address literacy issues, reading programs are essentials. Designing a high-quality primary grade reading programs is essentials to ensuring a pipeline of learners who remain in school, achieve educational success, and contribute to economic growth.

As stated in DO 14, s. 2018, the Department of Education (DepEd) supports Every Child a Reader Program, which aims to make every Filipino child a reader and a writer at his/her grade level. Thus, the DepEd through the Bureau of Learning Delivery-Teaching and Learning Division (BLD-TLD) shall continue to administer reading programs in public schools.

Reading success is crucial to academic success. Reading difficulties on the other hand hamper every aspect of a child's academic accomplishment. Thus, early reading is critical. Early reading instruction helps children develop superior reading skills and achieve greater academic success. When children fall behind in reading, they will struggle in other subjects and with schooling. They feel frustrated, lose motivation, and fall further behind, creating a downward spiral (Quimbo, 2021).

The Schools Division Office of Masbate Province launched and implemented different interventions to help improved the reading performance of the learners. Brigada PAGBASA (BP) was one of its intervention as a form of Brigada Eskwela, an after-school reading program in response to Hamon: Bawat Bata ay Bumabasa or DepEd 3B Initiative issued under DM 173, s. 2019. The Brigada Pagbasa program aimed to make every learner a reader by engaging partners and stakeholders to promote the culture of reading. All BE implementers are encouraged to conduct this partnership initiative for reading which serves as a platform to synergize education- related endeavors that immediately addresses literacy and numeracy learning gaps. This reading advocacy served as an avenue for all stakeholders to contribute possible solutions to improve the country's education system, especially in equipping the learners with 21st century skills. This program was religiously done in our school to cater the needs and to lessen the problem of our struggling readers.

Project SAGWAN (Shelve Achievement Gaps thru Wider Academic Networking) was also implemented in the SDO Masbate Province. It is a flagship program of the Curriculum Implementation Division (CID) that aimed to address the existing achievement gaps in literacy and numeracy. SAGWAN in English, PADDLE symbolizes the continued collaborative efforts of the SDO Masbate top management, supervisors, school heads and teachers in sailing with synergy towards the desired performance "port of destination".

Also with the BriGADA BASA (Bridging Generated Assistance from dedicated Advocates for Books Appreciation towards Students' Advancement), it is SDO Masbate reading program that provided various activities for the learners to read and learn while in the comfort of their homes. Parents and stakeholders are empowered to expand support to schools by extending assistance in cash, in-kind and workforce.

Every child deserves a STAR (Support Towards Advancement in Reading) is a program under the umbrella of BriGADA BASA with the following objectives: first is to augment needed intervention of K to 3 learners along reading, second is to address the learning and reading gaps caused by pandemic, third is to help learners of K to 3 meet grade level standards and last is to acknowledge and appreciate the effort of the school reading team and the stakeholders thru proper and recognizable forum.

In every intervention comes with a good result. For us to know the result, SDO Masbate Province implemented the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) with the partnership of the DepEd Central Office. It was initially conceived as a 5-minute start-up reading assessment designed to help teachers quickly determine the reading profiles of their G1-G3 learners and develop appropriate reading instructional strategies. The main goal of CRLA is to identify children who need additional support for learning.

Also the ABC+ Project was implemented in close collaboration with DepEd and focused on improving outcomes in early literacy, numeracy and socio-emotional learning in the country. USAID, through the ABC+ Project, has been supporting DepEd in implementing innovative approaches to ensure access to a quality education with interventions focusing on improving early reading, math and social and emotional skills for early grade children (kindergarten to grade 3 or K-3) in the Philippines. The said partnership is still on going as of today which as of now, USAID trained teachers on Early Grade Instructional for Multilingual Classrooms.

Based on the Division Memorandum No. 280, s. 2022, all schools in Masbate Province are mandated to utilize and administer the **Quick RAP (Reading Assessment Package)** for Grades 4-6 learners upon the opening of In-person classes for School Year 2022-2023. Quick RAP is an instrument used to assess the reading ability of grades four (4) to grade six (6) in all schools of Masbate Province Division.

This tool is crafted to quickly wrap up the reading aptitude of the learner within a 5-minute duration. The objective of this tool are (1) to determine the reading ability of the learners in grades 4-6 respectively, (2) to measure the learners' reading levels, abilities, disabilities, (3) to bridge the reading and comprehension gaps of the learners, (4) to support the learners' growth in the acquisition of the English language and (5) to utilize the sample remediation and intervention activities provided in the package.

Reading fluency is fundamental for academic development more broadly, the researchers said, because problems with this skill can interfere with students' ability to learn other subjects as they make their way through later grades. Maximino S. Lazaro Integrated School of San Pascual South District conducts regular reading assessment to determine the reading fluency of the learners and provide them with the necessary interventions.

However, the results of Schools Program Implementation Review and Performance Assessment (PIRPA) in terms of Quality of the School Key Performance Indicators indicates that there are non-readers in the intermediate classes and teachers shared sentiments with regards to the reading fluency of their learners. The results provide evidence about the pandemic's impact on learning especially among learners receiving less contact time with the reading teachers and/or subject teachers.

In Maximino S. Lazaro Integrated School, specifically in Grade 6, the learners' literacy rate in English is alarming based on the result of the Beginning of the School Year Administration of the Quick RAP. Quick RAP Administration categorized four reading profiles: LEVEL 1 **Grappling** (If WORDS' score is 0 to 10), LEVEL 2 **Coping** (If WORDS'

score is 11 to 20) LEVEL 3 **Establishing** (If the PHRASES score is 0 to 5) and LEVEL 4 **Advancing** (If PHRASES' score is 6 to 10).

Given the situation of the Grade 6 Grappling Readers in Maximino S. Lazaro Integrated School on literacy, this project aimed to help build the reading level of the grappling readers using the Project **SEL-P (Strategic Enhancement Learning-Package)**. This project provided reading activities using contextualized reading materials crafted by the proponents themselves.

Research Questions:

This study aims to improve the reading level of the Grade VI Grappling Readers of Maximino S. Lazaro Integrated School, Pinamandayan, San Pascual Masbate Province, School Year 2022-2023.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the reading level of the Grade VI learners before and after the implementation of the intervention?
2. How effective is Project SEL-P in improving the reading level of Grade VI Grappling Readers of Maximino S. Lazaro Integrated School?
3. What are the insights gained by the Grade VI learners on Project SEL-P?

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the research design, the respondents, the procedure of investigation, the tools used in data gathering, and the statistical tools applied in evaluating effectiveness of contextualized reading package to the reading level of grade 6 learners.

Methods Used

The proponents implemented the Project SEL-P (Strategic Enhancement Learning Package) in Improving Reading level of Grade VI Grappling Readers a contextualized tool kit to help build the reading level of struggling readers. The 9 Grade 6 Grappling readers of Maximino S. Lazaro Integrated School had a 30-minute session from 4:00 to 4:30 for 12 weeks. It started from February 5, 2024 up to April 29, 2024. They have been taught phonemic awareness, alphabet knowledge and decoding through the use of the Contextualized SEL-P. The proponents met with the parents of the identified participants and explained about the research study. The proponent provided the checklist and monitoring tool to see if they were able to keep track of their children (please refer under gathering methods). They met every Friday and in the absence of the proponents, the parents continued their weekly monitoring.

The proponents used the 3 methods for teaching reading by Dr. Orton and Dr. Gillingham, namely:

The Phonics Method

This concerned with helping pupils how to break words down into sounds, translate sounds into letters and combined letters to forms new words. In the beginning, progress maybe slow and reading out loud halting, but eventually the cognitive processes involved in translating between letters and sounds are automatized and become more fluent. The primary focus of phonics instruction is to help readers understand how letters are linked to sounds (or phonemes) to: (1) form letter-sound correspondences and spelling patterns and (2) help them learn how to apply this knowledge to their reading. Phonics instruction may be provided systematically or incidentally. This will be done by the proponents individually or with partners. In this part, the proponents will give the pupils the SEL-P tool for the first 1-3 weeks and allow the child to read on his own. The pupils can bring the provided SEL-P tool to his/her home to read and re-read with the help of guardian.

The Whole-word Method

This teaches reading at the word level. Because it skips the decoding process, pupils were not sounding out words but rather learning to say the word by recognizing its written form. Context was important and providing images can help. Familiar words here may initially be presented on their own, then in short sentences and eventually in longer sentences. In reality, 70-80% of content comprehension is based on knowing the meaning of words (Pressley, M. 2002). The proponents checked and monitored if their vocabulary increases or grow weekly for 3 weeks, because in this part, pupils begun to extract rules and patterns that they can use to read new words. This was strictly monitored by the proponents for 4-8 weeks to check the development of the Grappling readers using the contextualized SEL-P tool.

The Language Experience Method

Fluency is defined as the capacity to read quickly, accurately, and with suitable expression. In this part, pupils were able to read fluently, whether aloud or silently, in order to comprehend what they read. They were monitored by the proponents to determine if there is a significant improvement on the level of reading of the pupils using the contextualized SEL-P tool.

Fluent readers read in sentences and use appropriate intonation while reading aloud. Their delivery was fluid and expressive. Pupils who cannot read fluently have a choppy and unnatural tone to their voice. The remaining 4 weeks was done in this method. Those pupils may struggle with phonetic skills or just need additional practice with reading speed and smoothness. Fluency becomes increasingly critical as readers progress through the grades, as the amount of reading required increases considerably.

The table below showed the week number, reading materials to be read and methods of reading to be done. Reading materials were quality assured by the School

Quality Assurance Team, School Head as the chairman, 1 Master Teacher II as the Vice-Chairman, LR coordinator and reading teacher as the members.

During the validation of the contextualized SEL-P tool, the validators suggested that the contextualized materials should be done considering the context or level of the learners, that's why we used the method of Dr. Orton and Dr. Gillingham which started in the phonics method.

Spiral progression was reinforced in crafting the intervention tools.

Week Number	Reading Materials	Methods of Reading
Week 1	Word Family List	The Phonics Method
Week 2	Word Family List	The Phonics Method
Week 3	Basic Sight Words	The Phonics Method
Week 4	Basic Sight Words	The Whole-word Method
Week 5	Phrases	The Whole-word Method
Week 6	Phrases	The Whole-word Method
Week 7	Sentences	The Whole-word Method
Week 8	Sentences	The Whole-word Method
Week 9	Short Stories	The Language Experience Method
Week 10	Short Stories	The Language Experience Method
Week 11	Short Stories with Comprehension	The Language Experience Method
Week 12	Short Stories with Comprehension	The Language Experience Method

For Quantitative part, the literacy level of the respondents who fall under the Level 1 Profile (Grappling) in terms of Quick RAP reading profile was identified by utilizing the pretest and posttest Quick RAP Tools using the Division automated Class Record and Class Summary Scoresheets.

The proponents analyzed the significant improvement of both the Quick RAP result and Fluency test result by the end of the completion of the intervention by using the T-test which compare the means of two groups.

The T-test was used to determine whether there is a substantial difference between the pupils' pre-test and post-test results. This statistical test also was used to determine whether a process or treatment which is the Innovative Project SELP had effect on the reading fluency of the respondents.

For the Qualitative part, to analyze the data from the interviews during the FGD, transcriptions were used. This involved close observation of data through repeated careful listening (and/or watching). This assisted the proponents in identifying emerging themes. This familiarity with data and attention to what is actually there rather than what is expected can facilitate realizations or ideas which emerge during analysis.

To be able to effectively implement Project SEL-P, close monitoring was done through FGD's and the use of Monitoring Tool for parents. Every Friday during the Focus Group Discussion, the proponents collected the monitoring tool given to the parents ahead of time and each parent was asked of their experience in that particular week. Responses on whether the respondents finish the task for the day and the problems encountered during the session were noted.

Respondents of the Study

The participants of this study who received the 12-week intervention are the nine (9) Grade 6 pupils who belong to the Level 1 (Grappling) in English during the administration of Quick RAP of Maximino S. Lazaro Integrated School, Pinamandayan, San Pascual, Masbate Province, School Year 2022-2023. Purposive sampling was used to identify the respondents. Table 1 shows the frequency distribution and percentage of the participants.

Table 1
Distribution of Participants

Reading Level	Frequency	Percentage
Grappling	9	100%
Total	9	100%

There were 9 participants identified as grappling level during the pretest of QUICKRAP among grade 6 learners. They are the pupils who had difficulty in decoding words and reading phrases and needs assistance for them to build their reading fluency. Purposive sampling was used to identify the respondents. Table 1 shows the frequency distribution and percentage of the participants.

Data Gathering Tools

The proponents used the pre- experimental one group pretest-posttest design. The dependent variable is measured once before the intervention is implemented and once after the it is implemented.

Before the implementation of the Project SEL-P, the respondent underwent pretest first, after the 12 weeks' implementation, the proponent will conduct posttest to measure if the treatment is really helpful in improving the reading level of the identified respondent.

In gathering data to solve the problem, the proponents used the reading assessment tools such as the Quick RAP (CID, Masbate Province Division) and the Fluency Rubric (modified from Tim Rasinski-Creating Fluent Readers). The proponents utilized the Quick RAP pretest and posttest which will be answered by the respondents before and after the implementation of the Project SEL-P.

The results of the Quick RAP Administration were used to determine if there is a significant improvement on word accuracy and reading aptitude because it was only given a 5-minute duration. The Fluency rubric will also be used to monitor the progress of the fluency of the respondent especially once they have completed the intervention.

After the data were gathered, the proponents used the Quick RAP Class Record and Quick Rap class summary for tabulation and analysis provided by the CID, Masbate Province as data analyzing tool to determine the outcomes of the study.

The proponents gave a *Modified Study Lesson Monitoring Tool for Parents* to provide the parents a checklist to see if they were able to keep track of their children. This also determined whether they able to assist their children with the execution of the intervention. The proponents watched the respondents closely as they attempt to emulate the intervention study guide.

Table 2
Sample Monitoring Tool for Parents

WEEK & SESSION	Did the pupils finish the task for today? Yes or No, if not please leave a comment.	What problem or problems encountered during the session?
Week 1 Session 1 or W1 S1	<i>No!</i> <i>My child has to do his/her assignment in other subject.</i>	<i>Time management</i>

Every Friday, with the presence of the proponents and the parents of the respondents had the Focus Group Discussion. Parents' comments on intervention implementation, as well as research difficulties and concerns, were gathered. This is important because the proponents selected whether or not to depart from the intervention study guide that has been created.

After twelve weeks, a posttest along with phonological awareness, alphabet knowledge, decoding, word recognition, reading fluency were conducted to the learners.

Procedure of Investigation

The following were the processes that were observed by the researchers in order to realize the goals of the study.

Conceptualization of the Research Problem. The researcher identified why a study on a particular topic is needed. Since ideas generated were still broad and vague, the researcher had to redefine them. This process included identification and definition of the variables to be studied, development of the theoretical and conceptual framework of the study, formulation of the major and specific problems to be investigated and the formulation of hypothesis.

Approval of PROBE Research Title. Conceptualized study was then presented to the adviser for checking and for further corrections before it was presented to learning supervisor for its approval.

Securing Permit to Conduct the Study. After the approval of the paper, a letter securing permit and MOA from the school head of Maximino A. Lazaro Integrated School was made.

Preparation of the Instrument and Contextualized Reading Material. After the permit was approved, the researcher immediately prepared the data gathering tool based of the specific problems of the study. And create a contextualized reading material to be used in this research.

Administering and Retrieval of Questionnaires. The tool Quick RAP (CID, Masbate Province Division) and the Fluency Rubric (modified from Tim Rasinski-Creating Fluent Readers) used on the conduct of pretest and posttest. This were distributed personally to the respondents. Also, the monitoring tool for parents were also administered. This facilitated the researchers to answer and clarify questions needing further explanations. Besides, it was an opportunity to interview them. After they were accomplished, they were also collected personally. Hence, the questionnaires were retrieved, coded, tallied, and tabulated in order for appropriate statistical treatment can be applied.

Processing of the Data Gathered. The data were treated using appropriate statistical tools to ensure that correct analysis and interpretation of data be made. Analysis of the Result. The quantified results were placed in tabular form to facilitate

analysis and discussion. The analysis and interpretation were made to answer the specific problems raised in this study.

Writing and Submission of the Manuscript. After completing the data analysis and interpretation, the researcher prepared the manuscript and was submitted to the Learning Supervisor for approval and publication.

Statistical Tools

There were two statistical tools used to treat the data gathered for analysis and interpretation. A statistical software available in the internet was used.

Percentage. This tool was used to determine reading level of the respondents.

Paired sample T-Test. This was used to determine the significant difference between the pretest scores and posttest scores.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section is a discussion of the results of the study. Data were placed in tabular form to facilitate analysis and discussion.

To address literacy issues, reading programs are essentials. Designing a high-quality primary grade reading programs is essentials to ensuring a pipeline of learners who remain in school, achieve educational success, and contribute to economic growth. As stated in DO 14, s. 2018, the Department of Education (DepEd) supports Every Child a Reader Program, which aims to make every Filipino child a reader and a writer at his/her grade level. Thus, with reference to the said memorandum, a reading intervention was implemented.

A. Reading Level of Grade 6 Learners Before and After the Implementation of Project SEL-P

Several reading interventions were implemented in Maximino S. Lazaro Integrated School but still the existence of struggling readers is evident. For this reason, the proponents implemented the Project SEL-P (**Strategic Enhancement Learning Package**) in Improving Reading Level of 9 Grade 6 Grappling Readers using a contextualized reading learning package to improve English reading fluency of Grade 6 learners.

This study is in line with researches conducted by Bonganciso (2016) who found out that Contextualized Teaching and Learning's effects on the reading comprehension performance of thirty-three Bachelor of Science in Information Technology students were investigated. The pupils' reading comprehension performance improved significantly from the pretest to the posttest.

As a result, when reading activities are contextualized, positive benefits on learners' reading comprehension ability can be seen. Krause et al. (2016) stated that the three principles that support the use of content contextualization: prior knowledge, fostering conceptual change, and boosting metacognition, according to the author.

The table below shows the result before and after the implementation of the project.

Table 3
Reading Level of Learners Before and After the Implementation of the Intervention through Project SEL-P

Learners	Pretest Score			Reading Level	Posttest Score			Reading Level
	Words	Phrases	Sentences		Words	Phrases	Sentences	
	20	10	17		20	10	17	
A	3	2	1	Level 1	20	9	14	Level 4
B	2	3	1	Level 1	20	9	13	Level 4
C	1	3	2	Level 1	20	10	17	Level 4
D	1	2	1	Level 1	20	7	13	Level 4
E	0	2	0	Level 1	19	10	14	Level 4
F	0	1	0	Level 1	19	4	4	Level 3
G	0	2	0	Level 1	20	9	17	Level 4
H	0	1	0	Level 1	18	5	6	Level 3

I	1	2	1	Level 1	20	6	12	Level 4
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Table 4
Reading Profile of Learners Before and After the Implementation of the Intervention through Project SEL-P

Learners	Pretest Score (TOTAL SCORE 47)	Reading Profile	Posttest Score (TOTAL SCORE 47)	Reading Profile
A	6	Grappling	43	Advancing
B	6	Grappling	42	Advancing
C	6	Grappling	47	Advancing
D	4	Grappling	40	Advancing
E	2	Grappling	43	Advancing
F	1	Grappling	27	Establishing
G	2	Grappling	46	Advancing
H	1	Grappling	29	Establishing
I	3	Grappling	38	Advancing

The posttest results showed that out of 9 respondents who fall under Grappling or Level 1 during the pre-test, 7 or 77.78% were able to move to Level 4 or Advancing and 2 or 22.44 were able to move to Level 3 or Establishing. These results suggest the effectiveness of the implementation of Project SEL-P in improving the reading level of learners in any grade level and can also be used by other teachers.

As to the pretest result of the Quick RAP Administration for the Academic Year 2022-2023 of Maximino S. Lazaro Integrated School Grade 6 learners, out of 35 learners assessed, 25.71% or 9 are under Grappling; 2.86% or 1 is Coping; 34.29% or 12 are Establishing; and 48.57% or 17 are Advancing.

It was also observed by the teacher during the administration of Quick RAP that learners who fall under Grappling have word recognition problems and discovered that they had problems with consonant blends and consonant digraphs.

They maybe small in number but the results are quite alarming. Quimbo (2021) findings that when children fall behind in reading, they will struggle in other subjects and with schooling. They feel frustrated, lose motivation, and fall further behind, creating a downward spiral. Thus, it is important to assist the learners to improve their reading level.

For this reason, the proponents implemented the Project SEL-P (**Strategic Enhancement Learning-Package**) in Improving Reading Level of 9 Grade 6 Grappling Readers using a contextualized reading learning package to improve English reading fluency of Grade 6 learners. This project is in line with researches conducted by

Bonganciso (2016) who found out that Contextualized Teaching and Learning's effects on the reading comprehension performance of thirty-three Bachelor of Science in Information Technology students were investigated.

The pupils' reading comprehension performance improved significantly from the pretest to the posttest.

As a result, when reading activities are contextualized, positive benefits on learners' reading comprehension ability can be seen. Krause et al. (2016) stated that the three principles that support the use of content contextualization: prior knowledge, fostering conceptual change, and boosting metacognition, according to the author.

For starters, contextualized content training helps learners to use their past knowledge and solve problems more effectively. If topics can be tied to their daily lives, students will remember more knowledge. Second, when content contextualization exercises are participatory and engaging, students are motivated by the concept's relevance, which results in improved learning.

Finally, content contextualization allows students to reflect on their learning by connecting ideas from a familiar tangible context of an abstract thought, allowing them to distinguish their own personal associations with these ideas.

B. Effectiveness of Project SEL-P in Improving the Reading Level of Grade 6 Grappling Readers

Reading tools can be highly effective in improving the reading levels of grappling readers when tailored to their specific needs and implemented in a supportive context or it is within the context of the reader.

The effectiveness of this contextualized SEL-P (Strategic Enhancement Learning-Package) tool was very evident after the 12-weeks of implementation. This helped the grappling readers improved their literacy skills because the package was in accordance with the level of each learner.

During the implementation of this research, identified grappling readers showed progress every week and it was religiously monitored with the use of the monitoring tool and evaluated during the weekly Focus Group Discussion (FGD).

Blasoto and Manzanero (2019) observed the effectiveness of worksheets from tool kits in improving the reading comprehension of pupils. The Group Screening Test (GST) and the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI) show that students' reading performance in Filipino has improved.

Figure 1 below shows the result using paired sample T-test.

Figure 1: Paired Sample T-test Result

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T-TEST PAIRS=Pre WITH Post (PAIRED)
/CRITERIA=CI(.9500)
/MISSING=ANALYSIS.
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→ **T-Test**

[DataSet0]

Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 Pretest Score	3.44	9	2.128	.709
Posttest Score	39.56	9	7.038	2.346

Paired Samples Correlations

	N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1 Pretest Score & Posttest Score	9	.641	.063

Paired Samples Test

		Paired Differences				t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower				Upper
Pair 1	Pretest Score - Posttest Score	-36.111	5.904	1.968	-40.650	-31.573	-18.348	8	.000

In this study, the posttest results show that out of 9 learners under the Grappling Level showed significant improvement in their reading level. Seven (7) learners are on Advancing which means that their reading level is on Level 4 while two (2) learners belong to Establishing and/or the reading level is on Level 3. The pupils' reading level improved from Level 1 to Level 3 and Level 4 with a descriptive level of Establishing and Advancing.

It indicates that learners reading level had improved after the reading intervention. If on the pretest they can hardly recognize sounds, in the posttest, they can now read sentences with comprehension through the use of Phonics Methods, Whole- word Method and Language Experience Method.

Using paired sample T-Test, with 95% confidence level, result shows that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and posttest scores.

The result is supported by the study of Snowling and Hulme (2015) cited in Brooks (2016) proposed that it is possible to help struggling learners' oral language skills through strategies that focus on listening, vocabulary, and narrative skills. Higgins et al, (2017) recommend purposeful speaking and listening activity tools and strategies like giving them; books to read out loud and discussing them, activities to improve and broaden expressive and receptive language skills; collaborative learning where children can share thought processes; and students talking through their writing ideas, before beginning to

write. And Javed et al., (2015) commented that to increase students' comprehension skills, educators must use educational practices that foster critical thinking and pre-reading. Oral language is a crucial component of literacy development at every stage of a child's development. A focus on oral language abilities in early children, particularly those from impoverished families, can help both reading and writing (Educational Endowment Foundation, 2016 & 2017).

The result of this project offers a compelling evidence in favor of three methods of teaching reading by Orton and Dr. Gillingham technique significantly improve the Grappling Readers of 9 grade 6 learners. The findings unequivocally showed that Grade 6 reading level significantly improved as a direct result of the intervention. Orton and Dr. Gillingham methods of teaching reading shows to be successful method in promoting reading level, reading comprehension and facilitating meaningful learning experience especially that it had paired with the contextualized learning materials that is within the context of the learners.

After the conduct of interview with the parents as shown on their Monitoring Tool, it was discovered that the parent's collaboration and assistance in teaching listening, repeated, oral and pair reading as their children read the words, phrases and sentences contributed to the increased of reading level of the learners. Snowling and Hulme (2015) cited in Brooks (2016) proposed that it is possible to help struggling learners' oral language skills through strategies that focus on listening, vocabulary, and narrative skills. Higgins et al, (2017) recommend purposeful speaking and listening activity tools and strategies like giving them; books to read out loud and discussing them, activities to improve and broaden expressive and receptive language skills; collaborative learning where children can share thought processes; and students talking through their writing ideas, before beginning to write.

Conclusions

From the foregoing findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. It is concluded that teachers and parents' collaboration is important on improving the learners reading level. As DepEd 2021 reiterated teachers, parents, and other reading professional's collaboration foster and measure learners' reading skills.
2. Reading intervention strategies are crucial for supporting struggling readers and helping them improve their literacy skills. As proponents of this intervention, it is essential to reflect on the effectiveness of these strategies in order to make informed decisions about which interventions to implement and how-to best support learners.
3. This project with the support of the parents and school head, resulting in noticeable improvements in their reading level and fluency. From a word reader, they become phrase readers and later became sentence and paragraph readers. The proponents, reading teachers and parents work hand and hand for the successful implementation of Project SEL-P. It is therefore

concluded in this reflection that commitment, passion and perseverance are the most important things to accomplish a task like this.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

1. It is highly recommended that teachers can adopt the three method of teaching reading by Orton and Dr. Gillingham coupled with the contextualized learning package as their preferred reading intervention to the struggling learners. By integrating this method to their reading intervention, it can help to effectively uplift the literacy rate and learning loss.
2. School and district-wide can use of this method as part of their reading intervention to improve the reading level of the struggling learners is advocated. Embracing this method can lessen non-readers in school. Teachers are advised to benchmark, adopt and adapt this method in reinforcing learner's reading level as it has demonstrated effectiveness in facilitating meaningful reading experience. The effectiveness of this study was very evident. During the conduct of District Reading Assessment which was done after the last week of the implementation of this research, the assessment resulted that there is no identified non-reader in the Grade 6 class.
3. The perception of reading intervention implementation can vary depending on factors like effectiveness, accessibility and adaptability to individual needs. This intervention greatly helped the grappling readers to improve their reading skills which helped them to move to the next grade level. This greatly implies that the effectiveness of this intervention is evident. Teachers are advised to adopt this intervention to help lessen the struggling readers in the class. However, in contextualizing or crafting reading materials, teachers should consider the level of learners or their materials should be within the context of the learners. Overall, this project helped addressing reading difficulties and improving literacy skills among grappling readers.
4. To ensure their children's success in the intervention, parents must commit themselves to play their roles in the implementation of reading program. Thus, it is recommended to establish teacher-parent partnership to develop their children's love for reading and helped developed their reading skills.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to the implementation of the intervention, proponents secured parent consent to the child-participants. The proponents informed the beneficiary of the intervention as well as the adviser. Parents were informed of the status of their children in the literacy level that is why they immediately signed the parent consent considering that their

children will benefit the intervention. They fully entrusted the welfare of their children to the proponents provided that due care and precaution will be observed to ensure their safety.

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